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INGAME
Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation

INGAME

INGAME – Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation – A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy

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Lithuania National Report

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1. Introduction

1.1. Aim/Objectives of Report

The report is developed in the frames of the INGAME project (Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation - A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy) funded by the EU and represents one of the specific deliverables of Work Package 2 (Mapping the INGAME Ecosystem of Needs, Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of Work). The project intends increasing the skills and civic participation of young adults aged between 18 and 35 using an online game called INGAME.

The aim of the document is to overview the situation in Lithuania and to present the research on needs analysis implemented in the beginning of the INGAME project therefore to try to better understand needs and expectations of these young people with the aim to increase their role in the digital society.

Youth policy in Lithuanian legal acts is defined as a purposeful activity intended to resolve youth problems and to seek to create favorable conditions for the formation of the personality of a young person and his integration into public life, as well as an activity which has the purpose of achieving understanding and tolerance of society and individual groups thereof towards young people. Youth policy in Lithuania¹ is understood as the entirety of systems and measures, aspiring after the most favorable terms for personal maturity of a young person and successful integration into society. It is generally accepted to refer to structures of assistance (fields of socialization), subsidiary adding to the effort of a person and, especially, of a family, and helping to prepare a young person for independent life².

The document states that policy in Lithuania is developed in two directions:

- 1) ensuring the interests of youth in individual fields of public policy – education and science, culture, sports, work and employment, housing, health care, etc.
- 2) youth activities aimed at enabling young people to learn from experience and experiment (voluntariness, independence, autonomy).

The youth policy is shaped by the Lithuanian Ministry of Social Security and Labour; in the field of social security and labour, it is implemented by the Department of Youth Affairs, municipal authorities, other establishments and institutions in cooperation with non-governmental sector. In

¹ <https://jrd.lt/informacija-dirbantiems-su-jaunimu/metodiniai-leidiniai/el-biblioteka/jrd.pdf>

² <https://jrd.lt/informacija-dirbantiems-su-jaunimu/metodiniai-leidiniai/el-biblioteka/jrd.pdf>

2015, young people in Lithuania accounted for nearly 20 percent of the country's population. The number of young people as well as residents in other population groups is dropping as emigration of young people has been significantly speeding up the ageing of population.

Social inclusion, gender equality and participation have not been clearly and extensively explored in the youth policy documents, especially regarding digital possibilities of inclusion based on video games.

2. Key findings from Desk Research

2.1. Literature Review/National Context: Lithuania

There are existing many documents on the youth policies in Lithuania. One of the documents is the Law on Youth Policy Framework of the Republic of Lithuania³ stating that youth policy means a purposeful activity intended to resolve youth problems and to seek to create favorable conditions for the formation of a young person and his integration into public life, as well as an activity, which has the purpose of achieving understanding and tolerance of society and individual groups thereof towards young people. The document also mentions the following principles of the implementation of youth policy:

- 1) parity – state and municipal institutions and agencies as well as youth organisations are represented equally.
- 2) subsidiarity – youth-related decisions must be made at a level at which they are most effective.
- 3) interdepartmental co-ordination – when solving youth-related issues, state and municipal institutions and agencies communicate and co-operate with each other.
- 4) participation – youth-related issues are solved with the participation of young people and by co-ordinating them with youth or representatives of youth organisations.
- 5) informing – state and municipal institutions and agencies as well as youth organisations inform young people on the matters relevant to them in an acceptable and accessible form.
- 6) independence – young people themselves choose a field of activities, set its purposes, take an active part in it and are responsible for the fulfilment of the said purposes.
- 7) voluntariness – young people participate in a chosen field of activities of their own will and without pressure.

³ <https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/sites/youthwiki/files/gdllithuania.pdf>

- 8) self-governance – in their activity young people set down ways, forms, responsibility and evaluation of the implementation of the purposes of this activity.
- 9) communication and co-operation – youth organisations of Lithuania communicate and co-operate with youth organisations of Lithuania and other countries, state and municipal institutions and agencies, other natural and legal persons.

Social inclusion, gender equality and civic are based on the Legislative and policy framework related with The Law on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men (1998)⁴ and the Law on Equal Treatment (2005) provide for consistent and systematic implementation of programmes, measures and projects and are aimed at fostering de facto gender equality.

The Law on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men⁵ forbids any discrimination – whether direct or indirect – on the ground of sex, including sexual harassment. An independent Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson was appointed and its Office was established in 1999. The Law on Equal Treatment (2005) has been reformed several times (2001 (twice), 2002, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2016) and is now fully in line with the EU acquis and other international instruments. The Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson is responsible for the supervision and implementation of the Law on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men (1998) and the Law on Equal Treatment (2005). As a result of recommendations from various professionals and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), several improvements were made to the Law on Equal Treatment (2005) and the Law on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men (1998) in 2016. The amendments to the Law on Equal Treatment (2005) include, firstly, a prohibition to give any priority to either gender (except in cases foreseen by the law) in job advertisements for civil service recruitment. Secondly, potential employers are forbidden to ask jobseekers for any information on their family status, age (except in cases foreseen by law), private life, family formation and attitudes towards family planning. Thirdly, equal opportunities must be ensured for women and men in purchasing goods and services, including less favorable treatment of women because of pregnancy, childbirth, and nursing (except in cases foreseen by law).

Since 2012, Lithuania has compiled several key strategic documents: the National Programme on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2010–2014 (adopted in 2014); the National Programme on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015–2021 (approved in 2015); and the National Programme Implementation Plans for 2015-2017 and 2018-2021 (approved in 2018), respectively,

⁴ <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/488fe061a7c611e59010bea026bdb259?jfwid=q8i8817y0>

⁵ <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/488fe061a7c611e59010bea026bdb259>

which set out concrete actions, implementation deadlines, responsible institutions, state budget allocations needed for each step, and evaluation criteria⁶.

The total number of young people in Lithuania is 553989 (see fig1). However, there are implemented many national projects⁷ on social inclusion and gender equality.

Young People in Lithuania

Fig. 1. Youth in Lithuania by population and gender⁸.

Active Youth is a Lithuania-based for-purpose organisation that unites young leaders, thinkers and doers, those who seek change and those who make change with the goal to create social, cultural and educational impact for groups and communities in need working through organising and getting involved in youth mobility/training; as well as improving infrastructure and opportunities around us. There not found papers presenting digital tools and environments of young people inclusion , however the digitally excluded people are often the most socially excluded members of society and

⁶ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/countries/lithuania>

⁷ <http://www.dsti.lt/projects.php>

⁸ <https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/sites/youthwiki/files/gdllithuania.pdf>

that by helping them to gain digital skills we address wider social challenges and exclusion. There is no doubt digital inclusion enables people to be more socially included and overcome challenges. However, the strategy Lithuania 2030⁹ says that the society must recognize the rights of socially marginalized people, helping them to maintain dignity and play a full part in the society, be active participants as regards social inclusion policies and related actions; it also has to help combating the stereotypes and stigma, to preserve and enhance the quality of life, social wellbeing, especially as regards children, and equal opportunities for all.

2.2. Social inclusion in Lithuania

In general, the youth field contributes to healthy, prosperous, and sustainable democracies by trying to support the social inclusion of young people. To achieve social inclusion means to ensure all young people's human rights are protected, that all young people have the (human, cultural, social and financial) capacities and available opportunities to participate fully in the various life spheres (economic, social, cultural and political life), and attain a good standard of living and quality of life within their respective countries. The youth field takes up this challenge, and pays attention to those socially excluded, vulnerable or at risk, and seeks to ensure their greater participation in decisions that affect their lives (EU 2018)¹⁰

However, the main challenges related to social inclusion of young people in Lithuania are youth unemployment and integration in the labor market, non-formal education, and youth entrepreneurship. Socially excluded young people usually come from socially vulnerable families, from families whose parental rights were limited, from orphanages, youth living in remote/rural areas, children of migrant workers and immigrants, children of ethnic minorities, young people with any physical or mental disabilities and unemployed young people. Despite economic growth, increasing household revenues, and falling unemployment, inequality and poverty indicators in Lithuania remain among the highest in the European Union and raise the biggest concerns. Improved general and youth social security and reduced social exclusion remain among the social policy priorities. Lithuania pledges to step up social inclusion of young people, especially those who do not work or study and improve protection of workers, including immigrants. The focus has been placed on increasing opportunities of young people who are most distant from the labor market to participate in the implementation of active inclusion measures. Services for activation of voluntary activities of youth and the elderly, projects for the implementation of local employment initiatives, strengthening competencies of the disabled, sociocultural services and services of integration into the labor market have been planned for¹¹.

⁹ https://lrv.lt/uploads/main/documents/files/EN_version/Useful_information/lithuania2030.pdf

¹⁰ <http://mural.maynoothuniversity.ie/10219/1/REPORT-061118.pdf>

¹¹ <https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/en/content/youthwiki/4-social-inclusion-lithuania>

Social participation and integration statistics¹² shows present statistics on social participation in the European Union (EU) in 2015.

Fig. 2 Social participation and integration statistics (Eurostat statistics).

However, the games are the most appropriate way to be involved to the different activities. The fact that Kaunas is the real cradle of the Lithuanian gaming industry and the center of gaming culture is proven not only by successful game developing studios and specialized media channels operating in the city, but also by an active community of game developers and players who organize mass events which attract thousands of visitors and participants. These events range from the “Lan Party” in the Kaunas Sports Hall to the largest gaming convention in the Baltic States “GameOn” (<https://gameon.lt/en/>). During the GameOn event teams working together develop and pilot the games directly during the event.

2.3. Gender Equality in Lithuania

A new area of intervention in terms of video games and social inclusion is to address existing issues and gaps in relation to gender equality. The European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)¹³ Gender Statistics Database contains data on the numbers of women and men in key decision-making positions across a number of different life domains in order to provide reliable statistics that can be used to monitor the current situation and trends through time.

According to the statistics progress in gender equality in Lithuania since 2005 is showed below (see fig. 3).

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Social_participation_and_integration_statistics

¹³ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2019/LT>

Fig. 3. Progress in gender equality in Lithuania since 2005.

With 55.5 out of 100 points, Lithuania ranks 23rd in the EU on the Gender Equality Index. Its score is 11.9 points lower than the EU score. Between 2005 and 2017, progress towards gender equality did not improve in Lithuania; its score decreased by 0.3 points (- 1.3 points since 2015). Lithuania is progressing towards gender equality at a slower pace than other Member States. Lithuania's ranking is seven positions lower than in 2005.

Lithuania's scores are lower than the EU's scores in all domains, except for the domain of work. Gender inequalities are most pronounced in the domain of power (32.5 points) and time (50.6 points). Although much lower than other Member States, Lithuania's score is highest in the domain of health (79.8 points). Lithuania's score in the domain of money has improved the most (+ 7.7 points) since 2005. Progress has regressed in the domain of power (- 4.8 points) and time (- 2.9 points) and stalled in the domain of knowledge (+ 0.8 points).

Between 2005 and 2017, Lithuania's Index score declined. In this same period, the EU's score improved. Lithuania's direction of progress is therefore opposite to that of the EU.

The gaps identified is partly due to female-dominated professions, like education and social care, being generally worse-paid than fields dominated by men, according to Sodra.

Pay disparities exist within professions, too. The biggest gender gap is in IT, engineering, and medicine.

Over the past decade, the situation of young people in Lithuania has changed: their emigration increased, the unemployment of young people was quite high (in 2014, unemployment rate in the age group of 15–29 was 14.7 per cent) and their economic activity has changed. During the period of 2005–2014 about 438.5 thousand persons emigrated from Lithuania, of whom young people aged

14–29 made up 47.1 per cent. Thus, to evaluate the situation of and policymaking related to young people in Lithuania, the demand for statistical information about different young-age groups increased. To reach this aim, in 2015, the coverage of gender pay gap indicators was extended by more detailed young-age groups.

To monitor the existence of equal opportunities in the labor market for women and men, data on women's and men's economic activity are required to analyze. The gender pay gap by economic activity varies widely. In 2014, the largest gender pay gap was observed in enterprises engaged in financial and insurance (39.9 per cent), information and communication (28.8 per cent), manufacturing (25.2 per cent), other service (23.7 per cent), human health and social work (23.6 per cent), and wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (23 per cent) activities. The smallest gender pay gap was observed in enterprises engaged in construction, education, and public administration and defense, compulsory social security activities¹⁴.

However, there are no games to be used for gaps reduction in gender equality area in Lithuania.

2.4. Civic participation in Lithuania

Civic participation refers to participating in your community to develop it with the help of your knowledge, skills and values, to make a difference in your society. The goal of civic participation is to raise the standard and quality of life in your community, through commitment and motivation. Young people are considered very important in civic participation because they bring new and innovative ideas!

Civic participation is important because it teaches us how to live and work together, appreciating different opinions, values and beliefs in a tolerant manner. Through civic participation you become aware of difficulties, social problems and moral questions in your society, and are aware that there are possibilities to change and build a community. Only through active engagement do people get involved in their communities to make change for a better future.

According to the Civil Society Institute, citizen participation in various civic activities was lower last year, and almost three-quarters of people do not belong to any sort of organization.

One very important factor that gets people involved in various civic activities is whether their social circles, their friends, acquaintances or family members, include people who would invite and encourage them to get involved. Unfortunately, with what we've been seeing in Lithuania over the past few years, 70% of Lithuanian residents have never been invited or encouraged to join any sort of activity. It's important that those who are engaged invite people close to them¹⁵.

¹⁴

https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/stats/documents/ece/ces/ge.30/2016/WS/WP10_Lithuania_Ambrozaitiene.pdf
¹⁵ <https://en.delfi.lt/culture/civic-engagement-in-lithuania-is-falling.d?id=70800016>

In 2019, the key civic engagement activities included charitable donations (39% of the respondents involved), voluntary environmental cleanup (32%), and engagement in local communities' actions (26%). However, participation in these activities has been steadily declining for the last decade. In comparison to 2012, the number of persons donating to charities declined by 9%, participation in voluntary environmental cleanup declined by 22%, and local community engagement declined by 11%. 2019 saw a growth in only one type of civic activities: signing petitions online (23%) and offline (13%). Engagement in all other activities showed either a slight decline or fluctuated within the margin of statistical error. Participation in civic organisations and movements remained notably stable (8%)¹⁶. There are also mentioned that the Civic Empowerment Index consists of the following four dimensions: civic activeness, potential civic activeness, conception of civil society's influence, and civic activity risk assessment.

We found that there are implemented many projects related with civic engagement, however, there are no mentioned gamified methods of involvement or participation.

2.5. Good Practices

Internationally Stewart and Misuraca (2013) says that previous research has demonstrated how 'conventional' ICTs such as the PC and internet applications can support socio-economic inclusion processes for populations at risk of exclusion such as migrants, youth at risk, and the elderly and their careers. Recent growth of research and commercial activity in the use of digital games for non-leisure activities and the promise of gamification as a building block of social innovation promoted DG CNCT and the JRC-IPTS to launch a study, Digital Games for Empowerment and Inclusion. The goal was to better understand of how this hugely popular media form is being applied to issues of concern for social inclusion policy and inform future policy options. The authors (Stewart and Misuraca, 2013)¹⁷ also says that More than any other area of the ICT industry, the games industry has exploited the interactive multimedia potential of the technology, allowing creative development of new media forms, and leading the development and mass commercialization of graphical and input interfaces far beyond 'office' IT. While digital games (the software as opposed to the hardware) are computer software packages,¹⁰ they are simultaneously cultural and media products. They are built on the heritage of film, graphic arts, theatre, television and literature, but they also have the unique dimension of 'interactivity'.¹¹ Since games creatively combine multimedia, narrative, drama, competition, networks, and interactivity in rich and multitudinous forms highlights two issues important for policy: i) to produce these products, the digital game workforce has to be highly multi and interdisciplinary, often requiring staff with multiple skill sets, and ii) the industry falls across the 'technology' and 'culture media' sectors, with implications for policy support and intervention.

Currently in Lithuania e-Inclusion issues are getting more and more attention in Lithuania not only from state institutions but also from private sector. Success of some e-Inclusion projects which can be used as good practice examples from Lithuania usually lies in public–private partnership, bottom-up initiative and down to earth solutions of e-Inclusion problems. However governmental initiatives are still more in the form of conceptual and declarative

¹⁶ <http://www.civitas.lt/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/CIVIC-EMPOWERMENT-INDEX-2019.pdf>

¹⁷ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC77656/jrc77656.pdf>

documents than in real actions. This clearly shows analysis of state institutions' Web sites adaptability to the needs of disabled persons. Moreover, only a small amount of state financial sponsorship is allocated for the implementation of e-Inclusion projects

However, gamification could be used more effectively in the social and civic inclusion see the example of project PROMIS (<http://www.selfid.eu/>)

The largest gaming convention in the Baltic States "GameOn" (<https://gameon.lt/en/>). During the GameOn event teams working together develop and pilot the games directly during the event.

Therefore, Kaunas university of Technology is one of the leaders in Lithuania working in the games research and industry collaboration, by establishing startups for games developers. KTU is mainly focuses on the research and the models of gamification and the busines sector is focused on the games design. Educational gamification solutions are implemented directly at the University by The Virtual Technologies Laboratory. See some examples bellow.

As example of the 360-video game developed at KTU is presented by National museum (see fig. 4). The aim of this solution is to present the vehicles which are used nowadays in the Lithuanian armed forces. The technological solution includes the following three products: a virtual tour for the web, a virtual tour for virtual reality (Oculus platform) and a 3D shooting game created for virtual reality (Oculus platform). Virtual tour (for both web and VR) includes the M113 armored personnel carrier, a helicopter and a military airplane (Spartan). High-quality panoramic images were taken using stereoscopic photography so that the depth is sensible when viewing in VR application. A virtual tour for the web is accessible here: <http://www.virtualvizija.lt/projektai/muziejus/>.

Fig. 4. The 3D game depicts a training session.

The 3D VR game depicts a training session of the present days. The environment is modelled to be a generic shooting range for training. The player shoots from an M3 Browning machine gun that is mounted on an M113 armored personnel carrier. The game turned out to be very successful. Its mobility allows the museum to take it to various

trips. Moreover, the look and feel of the game as well as the ability to compete for the highest score is attractive both to the young learners and to the adults.

The participants could be engaged not only to see but also to participated in the different activities implemented in real life empowering social and civic engagement, gender equality and social participation, establishing the appropriate framework, digitally empowering youth.

2.6. Issues/Problems

The literature review shows that there is a big gap in the video games industry specialized in social inclusion showing the need of the project like INGAME. The research-based needs analysis will allow us to take a design on the gamification method and technology for implementation Video games based social inclusion.

3. Research results: questionnaires

3.1 Findings from field-based research

This section presents the findings of the research actions taken with participants i.e. (1 questionnaire) young persons aged 18-35, (2 questionnaire) the relevant stakeholders, and (3 questionnaire) the direct target group youth.

3.1.2 Focus group: Young Persons Aged 18-35

The first questionnaire was intended for Young Persons Aged 18-35. Totally 5 responses we got from the group declaring 20 % school and 80 % work status. According to the gender respondents represents 40 % male and 60 % female and according to the age there were involved two age groups, i.e. 60 % respondents of 31-35 years and 40 % respondents of 21-25 years (see fig. 5)

Fig. 5. Respondents by age.

Respondents were asked to specify what is civic engagement for them. Among answers there was mentioned (1) a nice way to improve our lives; (2) participation in the voluntaries work; (3) activeness in the public life; (5) volunteers participation and engagement and help to society in different actions.

Therefore, the respondents identified the activities they think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement, i.e. (1) equal rights for young woman; (2) individual or group activity addressing of public issues; (3) possibly to show the ways/examples that could engage to participate in the public life; (4) gamification could involve to the real situations of life.

Respondents mentioned the policies, practices, and interventions for promoting young civic engagement, social inclusion, and gender equality and how they should improve or change. Three respondents out of five mentioned gender equality actions and one mentioned action on non-ethical hunting.

There were mentioned some new technologies that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality, i.e. (1) serious game and gamification in VLE; (2) virtual reality engaging to the public life; (3) showing good practice cases of the real life; (4) online gaming for education.

We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action. Respondents also mentioned that (1) it is important that the game won't be too complicated so that anyone with no experience can go through several levels, interactive, (2) friendly environment, (2) attractive, (3) possibly based on levels, (4) the game could be in VR technology, or interactive, based on levels, engaging, involving; (5) attractive, inclusive, engaging.

3.1.3 Group 2: Stakeholders

Another questionnaire was intended for stakeholders. We totally got 7 stakeholders' responses, totally 28,6 % male and 71.4 % female. According to the age totally participated 4 groups out of 5 (see fig. 6).

What is your age?
7 atsakymai

Fig. 6. Stakeholders by age.

Stakeholders identified their type of organization (see fig. 7)

What is the type of your organization? Please select from below.
7 atsakymai

Fig. 7. Stakeholders' organizations.

The respondents answered what factors influence the civic engagement of young adult: (1) beliefs, feedback, interaction, fun; (2) the development of the new technologies; (3) schooling, personal interests, upbringing, public initiatives; (4) capacity for creativity and innovation; (5) example of famous people, moral and political issues, values coming from family and environment, thinking about future; (6) civic engagement of young adult depends on sociodemographic factors. For e.g., women could be more engaged in organizational citizenship, and men could have a higher dimension of civic value. The mental and physical health could be counted as a civic engagement factor as well. For e.g., women could become volunteers on promoting healthy eating habits which reveals the feminine nature, men could volunteer for public security which reveals the masculine nature of a

men. I think that recognition, inspiration as well as personal values could have an impact on civic engagement of young adult.

(7) at kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?

There were mentioned by respondents the activities that outline the importance of this type of engagement, i.e. (1) motivation related activities (proper feedback, gamification, fun); (2) the implementation of the important situations for young adults in the civic engagement; (3) engaging initiatives that generate youngsters' interest; various events, discussions, role plays, etc.

Engage and communicate with young people in an open, friendly and business-like way, stimulate creative and innovative capacities in young people, and to have a sense of direction, enable young people to think critically, to express their desires, to formulate goals, and to see through commitment, have the competence to act as mentors, advisors and role models, formal education or the world of work; (4) public actions, activities which show that people can change their and others lives; (5) relevant and actual nowadays topics, valuable and creative tasks, recognition could increase the participation of young adult in public life. Moreover, I think that the way ho to involve young adults should relate to social media.

Therefore, the discussion was organized on the main difficulties they face in involving young people in civic engagement activities. There were mentioned (1) lack of effective motivation; (2) people don't understand importance of civic activities; (3) the culture of the civic activities need to be developed; (4) the lack of the actual elements for young adults; (4) motivation, engagement; (5) lack of motivation, isolation (digital Issues, virtual life), a doubt in the idea; (6) involving young people in civic engagement activities are connected with a relevance of an idea and with a motivation and recognition (from the parents and society side maybe education institution as well).

However, there were mentioned several successful initiatives aimed to improve civic participation of young people and their attention to social inclusion or gender equality issues, i.e. (1) evaluation of their work, positive feedback from everyone (management, people), other methods to maintain the motivation; (2) the involvement in the movements for ecological life; (3) *Laisves (Eng. Freedom)* TV organizes a lot of initiatives like that in Lithuanian schools. The initiatives are successful, because students get encouraged by famous, highly respected famous people; such initiatives also address

young people's values and interests; (4) well planned engagement, gamified inclusion, (5) Red Nose Initiative - Young doctors wear red noses and visit hospitals like clowns to support children patients psychologically; (6) Big Brother Big Sister initiative; (7) the environment cleaning initiative called "Let's do it". The most important aspect of this event is that students could feel that they are a part of community which cares; (8) example is related with a study process where students can solve different problems of local society. The success point of this initiative is related with a relevant and creative task, also the trust which comes from the side of a teacher.

Respondents are aware of mentioned technologies and approaches, i.e. (1) technologies for game-based learning, but for different topics, mainly language learning; (2) gamification for study projects but never used for social inclusion and /or gender equality; (3) influencers with blogs; (4) The simple reason why the new technologies should be included in various activities is based on the generation features. Usually I include the game-based learning approach into my lectures.

However, there is opinion that currently there are a lot of such solutions developed around the world, esp. during ERASMUS projects (I would anticipate) and never needed to use them in my personal or professional life.

Respondents provided several opinions important for developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action, i.e. (1) a lot of this type of games (serious, educational) have imbalanced development focus. They tend to sideline the gameplay and game design part of development. It's necessary to strike perfect balance; (2) a game need to have the properties that has a normal addictive online game; (3) project goals should not overwhelm the game itself; (4) game should be oriented towards quality (professional design, models, sounds, etc...), better less scope than less quality; (5) a game should include some form of gamification and could use social networks; (6) one of the most important aspects of any kind of learning is relevance and authenticity; (7) when it comes to virtual learning, I would also consider interactivity, connectivism, engaging tasks, gamification aspects, and high quality graphics. simulation would be more engaged; (8) a possibility to construct different scenarios with different attributes for the students. I would be very interest in having a possibility to control and change some rules during the simulation process.

3.1.4 Group 3: Target Group

Totally 30 responses were provided by target group members. Gender balance is shown by responses 50 % female and 50 % male participated in the research. The age distribution is also well balanced by inviting all different age groups to provide responses (see fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Targets age groups.

Totally 93 % of respondents participates in the work activities. However, we can see the distribution of respondents in the different work activities per sector (see fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Different work activities.

There are a lot of opinions on what does civic engagement means, i.e. (1) Opportunity to participate when decisions that are important to society and the community are made; (2) some activities, related to public concern, making something better for society, city or country; (3) Opportunity to influence others' well-being as well as improve myself; (4) involvement to the city/public activities; (5) volunteering; (6) It is a good way to

address public concern and help others in our community, for example people should be involved in voting or protesting; (6) It is necessary to be part of civic engagement as long as It serves for Education, knowledge and social activity; (7) patriotism, one of values of life; (8) for me it means self-realization; (9) contributing to public and university life, participating in solving problems, socialization, collaboration, realization of my knowledge and skills; (10) it means participating in some civic initiatives, like helping to clean our parks and areas after winter; donating to some charities, signing petitions, etc.; (11) team work for free; (12) new opportunities, communication.

It is quite low rate of the respondent's participation the different civic activities in Lithuania (see fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Participation in the civic initiatives.

However, the respondents mentioned some initiatives: (1) regarding to political policies in European Parliament; (2) Unethical hunting; (3) Volunteering work in PICNIK KAUNAS (national event presenting innovations in IT); (4) Gender equality; (5) Social and psychological support, giving information (support service); (6) to present good practice women in IT; (7) Environmental protection.

The respondents identify that technology could play a role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation, i.e. (1) in terms of information distribution; (2) Technology involves the younger generation, but live communication is more conducive to a sense of community and involvement and empathy; (3) through the media and social networks; (4) it makes communication easier and more participants can be involved; (5) technology could help to be involved to the activities and to share the practical information; (6) help to understand the problems and possible solutions; (7) technologies are growing and getting better and better very quickly, so it could play a role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation soon; (8) just a tool to present; (9) makes people aware of social injustices and engages them to participate; (10) a visualization tool to engage or to

help to understand the problem; (11) expand the target group by involving more people into the civic engagement using social network, web based technologies, electronic billboards and more; (12) technologies gives opportunity to reach broader audiences, everybody who are using internet are equal (clothing, surrounding, device cannot be seen, judged). Not sure about amounts of people who have no opportunities to use mobile devices, internet, phone... but more and more people even from poor surrounding have smart phones, internet; (13) to maintain the motivation; (14) an important facilitator of social inclusion for people with disabilities into society as it helps to deliver of real-time services that can enable individuals to learn (even fully participate in education), work, socialize, shop, and interact with the community without being subject to physical barriers. In such way it could increase people's quality of life (15) technology could play a role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation by providing people interactive experiences about these subjects; (16) a game which focuses more on cooperation where everyone need to participate to achieve their main goal and also it is important that it does not provoke competition so that everyone is happy with themselves.

Aware of game-based learning initiatives is very different however, the respondents mentioned several practices: (1) Design thinking; theories of game urbanism (for example: <https://www.game-cities.com/>); (2) DuoLingo; (3) on prevention, health care; (4) Chemistry learning based on VR; (5) Kerbal Space Program - is a physically accurate space shuttle launching game. You try to create your space shuttle in a way that it could lead to a specific space mission. World of warcraft - Teaches you how to manage your character and teaches you English better than many books that claim to teach English. You can socialize with people; (5) while playing a certain game, you learn skills that you later use in real world; (6) Educative games, programs like Duolingo, Code combat; (7) GameON; (8) History lessons at Virtual museums exhibition; (9) project "Video games for teachers", Apps development for Social and Emotional Learning, which is also based on gamification; (10) Non-formal education initiatives for KTU students, the badge craft system; (11) Facebook city-building and civic education game "Our City"; (12) The game-based learning initiatives are great because they could be immersive and fun, which could help people learn difficult or boring subjects without researching plain text materials.

Respondents mentioned several initiatives on young people's civic engagement like (1) volunteering

<https://www.delfi.lt/news/daily/lithuania/sanciai-nerimsta-ir-toliau-aktyviai-priesinasi-naujos-gatves-statyboms.d?id=81168993>; <https://m.kauno.diena.lt/naujienos/kaunas/menas-ir-pramogos/ar-kopustu-laukas-sanciuose-taps-traukos-centru-799124>;

(2) Engagement through education, for example, participation in international Erasmus projects, sharing of different experiences in discussions and dialogue to deepen self-awareness and understanding of community for possible future actions, doing workshops all together and etc. (3) serious games in real life environment; (4) action before smoking; (5) volunteering work mostly popular among young people, it is engaged to participate even in schools (kids must have 10 h. per year, later universities, and then already it is for fun); (6) any volunteering work (food, bank, dog shelter); (7) it is difficult to say if they are really "best practices", but I was impressed by such actions like organizing blood donation events when academic community can donate blood at their faculties (8) free museums days to engage young people to come; (9) events like game jam.

Moreover, the gamification could be used to enhance critical reflection on social and political circumstances of young adult, i.e. (1) it could provide a better framework of reference, introduce more external motivators, thus somewhat increasing motivation; (2) through engaging activities and discovery of relevant topics; (3) It helps to involve young people; (4) Virtual reality-based games can improve many skills; (5) gamification can help in the political actions as well; (6) gamification should take race, gender, religion and free will of people into account. Give freedom to reflect ideology of player and not be punished because of this. Not discriminate because of his/her gender or race or religion. More interactive and task solving should be involved; (7) gamification can be used as a tool to maintain the motivation to participate more and acquire deeper knowledge about social and political circumstances.

Young adult could find themselves alienated by traditional methods of instructions, therefore the use of gamification could provide a partial solution to the decline in learners' motivation and engagement the schooling/university system is facing today. Specifically, the educational environment in Education institutions (schools, colleges, universities) could benefit a lot from gamifying not only their graduate recruitment strategies, but also the course content and curricula.

However the most successful activities and practices for fostering civic participation, social inclusion and gender equality among young people are identified: (1) competitions; (2) Workshops and debates; (3) exhibitions, (4) round-tables/debates; (5) diversity-days with games; (6) volunteering at

organizations, working on these issues; (7) virtual exhibitions; (8) meetings with experienced professionals.

Another opinion is that Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Games (MMO-RPG) give most successful activity especially if communication and collaboration is involved. Roundtables/debates are another successful way of exploring the idea of another person and discovering beautiful differences among people. Workshops - are very powerful because most of the time knowledge is involved rather than gender difference or race or any other discriminating factor. It could change the idea of people who are passionate to learn but less equal.

The competition element is always attractive to young people, so competition on photographs could be successful. Also, exhibitions, diversity days with games.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Key results of research

The processes of social inclusion, gender equality and participation are becoming important in the nowadays society. However, founded issues are not well discussed in the national level and need to be improved by using video games. Respondents' answers show that the theoretical level is quite well understandable, but there are no practical simulation and/or video games-based implementation practices, what could help for better integration into society. Furthermore, the responses about use of technology show engagement and less practical involvement. The gap shows that the INGAME project is a very important initiative for binding together and reinforcing both the domain of gaming and social inclusion processes in Lithuania.

It is widely accepted that ICT have a potential to play a major role in creating a more inclusive society. Gamification products and services with measurable benefits can enrich people's lives. Especially people at risk of social, economic, or digital exclusion may benefit from purposefully created digital services and equipment. Gamification can improve the quality, efficiency and effectiveness of public services offered by national, regional, and local administrations by meeting the needs of all citizens and businesses. The differences in possibilities to use gamification among various social groups and these differences form a new form of social exclusion – digital divide.

4.2. Recommendations for future action

The future actions that could be added in the future contributions of the INGAME project are based on the successful activities and practices for fostering civic participation, social inclusion and gender

equality among young people are identified: (1) competitions; (2) Workshops and debates; (3) exhibitions, (4) round-tables/debates; (5) diversity-days with games; (6) volunteering at organizations, working on these issues; (7) virtual exhibitions; (8) meetings with experiences professionals.

5. References

- EASEA. (2019). Inclusive programs for young people. Retrieved on June 20, 2020 from:
<https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/en/content/youthwiki/44-inclusive-programmes-young-people-lithuania>
- ELGE. (2019). Gender equality index. Retrieved on June 20, 2020 from:
<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2019>

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